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Research and Innovation Action

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D9.2 Press releases and social media presence

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Executive Summary

Disclaimer

The template of this document will not be the official template of the BIM4REN project. The new template will be created by COMET in the frame of WP9 by the end of 2018

This document (D9.2) contains a description of the actions undertaken to set-up and launch BIM4REN's Press Releases and Social Media by M2, as part of the project's communication activities as described in Task 9.2. The actions include a first press release of the BIM4REN project and setting-up social media presence via Twitter and LinkedIn and their associated activities. We also present a quick overview of the first news or discussions around the BIM4REN project that prove the communication of the project has started and that it is on a good path.

These actions were set forward early in the project to start involving and creating awareness to potential stakeholders and to serve as stepping stones for the communication and networking actions which will be established in the Communication Strategy (D9.3) by M3 (end of December 2018), which will integrate more materials.

Included in this document are screenshots of the activities to date. It should be noted that, as an ongoing project-long effort, upcoming communication activities may modify and impact how these two activities will continue to be developed. Mainly the corporate image, which is still under design and review for the upcoming release of the public website (D9.1) and Public Communication Materials (D9.4), which will affect the templates, documents and contents produced for these two activities; and the Communication Strategy (D9.3) which will define and expand on the long-term communication and dissemination approach and KPI's.

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1. Introduction

The actions and materials presented in this deliverable (D9.2) showcase the first steps taken to launch the communication efforts of the project via Social Media and Press Releases, as part of our international communication and dissemination campaign to raise awareness of the BIM4REN project. Through these and other means, the consortium plans to promote the concept and results of the BIM4REN project to selected stakeholders and multipliers such as BIM and energy simulation software developers, industrials, architects, engineers and construction companies, building owners, policy makers, standardisation and certification institutions, the general public and end-users.

BIM4REN's communication activities intend to have a high impact during the project, having set a goal of 10 million views across all partner feeds and targeting a broad range of stakeholders and the general public, which is why press releases and social media were set in place early in the project: to begin creating awareness of the project and to start the network of potential stakeholders and multipliers needed throughout the project life-cycle to reach these goals.

Our overall strategy to engage our stakeholders via Social Media and Press Releases will be further detailed in BIM4REN'S Communication Strategy (D9.3 – M3) and will be better represented virtually and physically as we conclude other communication activities detailed in Task 9.2, mainly the project visual identity, public website (D9.1 – M4), public dissemination materials (D9.4 – M6) and clustering activities (D9.8 – M6).

This deliverable is part of WP9's Task 9.2 (BIM4REN Communication Activities), whose main objective is to set up key elements and tools for a creative and comprehensive communication effort and the effective dissemination of the project.

In this document, the actions put in place are presented together with the relevant descriptions, screenshots and links. As an ongoing part of the communication activities, they will be updated throughout the project life cycle with news and information according to the communication strategy and to support the rest of the work packages as well as the long-term objectives of the BIM4REN project.

2. Press Releases

The BIM4REN project will use press releases as a mean to reach out to traditional and online media to communicate on the relevant events and/or news that the consortium wishes to mark as important milestones, in order to boost awareness of the project and maximise impact on potential stakeholders, multipliers, general public and end-users. The project has a goal of issuing at least 10 press releases.

EBC will be the partner in charge of coordinating the press releases during the project. For dissemination of press releases, a form will be made available to the partners a form to be filled out and sent to the communication team. Once issued, they will also be shared via social media and will be available for download on the public website.

2.1. Press release to launch the project

The first press release was written by the partners of the consortium, led by EBC and finalized on the 10th of November 2018. It was issued after the project Kick-off Meeting in order to launch the project and start creating awareness via Social Media. (Figure 3 and 4).

The full content of the document can be seen below and is also available online at the following link: <https://mailchi.mp/c273c7b383c2/ebc-bim4ren-project-kickoff-bordeaux>.

Figure 1. Screenshot of EBC’s Twitter account where Press Released was initially shared

Press release

Easy-to-use BIM tools for collaborative construction energy renovation works: new Horizon 2020 project BIM4REN

Brussels, 29th October 2018 – With 3 million enterprises and 18 million workers, the construction industry represents around 9% of the European Union GDP. However, the sector is among the least digitalised industries of the European economy. The construction industry is also responsible for about 40% of final energy consumption in the EU and generates 36% of greenhouse gases in Europe. In this context, the EU-funded project BIM4REN, gathering 23 construction stakeholders under the lead of French Research and Technology Centre (RTO) Nobatek/INEF4, aims at developing user-friendly Building Information Modelling (BIM) tools and services in the field of energy renovation of existing buildings. The kick-off meeting of this 4-year project, financed up to € 7 million by Horizon 2020, took place on 24-25 October in Bordeaux, France. The vision of the project was already exposed to some BIM experts, renovation practitioners or public bodies in a public conference called ["Digital Conference 2018 - Digitalise or die: New tools for the construction sector"](#), attracting 80 people to discuss about the need of a digital revolution of the construction sector to improve collaboration, productivity and quality.

Digital transformation is happening at a slow pace in the European construction industry. This means a huge gap between the theoretical digital opportunities and construction on-site realities. More energy efficient buildings require innovative or adapted methods and tools for construction professionals, especially construction SMEs, and efficient and collaborative processes along the whole construction value chain. The project **"BIM based tools & technologies towards a fast and efficient RENovation of residential buildings - BIM4REN"** aims at introducing state-of-the-art and easy-to-use BIM tools for collaborative construction energy renovation processes to face these issues, building in particular on the results of three pilot sites (Paris, San Sebastian and Venice) providing solid elements to evaluate the performance of the BIM4REN innovations.

BIM is too often perceived as a collection of complex tools and work methods that require several weeks of heavy training, often inaccessible to small companies from a financial and practical point of view. **The BIM4REN partnership aims to make full use of BIM technology to improve the energy efficiency in situations of refurbishment and renovation of the existing building stock, with a particular attention for construction micro, small and medium-sized enterprises.** Top-notch RTOs active in the built environment domain ([Nobatek](#), [CSTB](#), [Tecnalia](#), [TNO](#) and [Fraunhofer ISE](#)) will work alongside key industrial actors ([EDF](#), [CMB Carpi](#) and [ATI Project](#)), Universities ([Aachen University](#) and [Vilnius University](#)), R&D firms ([R2M Solution](#), [COMET](#) and [Ekodenge](#)), technology providers ([IES](#), [EnerBIM](#), [WiseBIM](#), [VRM](#) and [AEC3](#)), SME contractors ([Kursaal](#) and [Termoline](#)), a social housing organisation ([Logirep](#)), the [Green Building Council - Italy](#) and the [European Builders Confederation EBC](#), the European organisation representing micro, small and medium-sized construction companies.

"Our sector is 94.1% of companies with fewer than 10 employees and 99.4% of less than 49 employees; however, while the digital transformation of the construction sector cannot be done without SMEs, these companies do not have access to it or do not use it", says Eugenio Quintieri, EBC Secretary General, who adds: *"Digital tools and methods make it possible to alleviate heavy tasks and avoid doubling actions, to improve the image of our professions, to go towards more efficiency, more energy saving and better communication within the value chain, as long as they are financially and technically accessible for SMEs and constitute a real added value!"*

Figure 2. EBC's Official Press Release

2.1.1. November BIM4REN Press Release

Easy-to-use BIM tools for collaborative construction energy renovation works: new Horizon 2020 project BIM4REN

Brussels, 30 October 2018 - With 3 million enterprises and 18 million workers, the construction industry represents around 9% of the European Union GDP. However, the sector is among the least digitalised industries of the European economy. The construction industry is also responsible for about 40% of final energy consumption in the EU and generates 36% of greenhouse gases in Europe. In this context, the EU-funded project BIM4REN, gathering 23 construction stakeholders under the lead of French Research and Technology Centre (RTO) Nobatek/INEF4, aims at developing user-friendly Building Information Modelling (BIM) tools and services in the field of energy renovation of existing buildings. The kick-off meeting of this 4-year project, financed up to € 7 million by the EU programme Horizon 2020, took place on 24-25 October in Bordeaux. The vision of the project was already exposed to some BIM experts, renovation practitioners or public bodies in a public conference called "[Digital Conference 2018 - Digitalise or die: New tools for the construction sector](#)" attracting 80 people to discuss about the need of a digital revolution of the construction sector to improve collaboration, productivity and quality.

Digital transformation is happening at a slow pace in the European construction industry. This means a huge gap between the theoretical digital opportunities and construction on-site realities. More energy efficient buildings require innovative or adapted methods and tools for construction professionals, especially construction SMEs, and efficient and collaborative processes along the whole construction value chain. The project "***BIM based tools & technologies towards a fast and efficient RENovation of residential buildings - BIM4REN***" aims at **introducing state-of-the-art and easy-to-use BIM tools for collaborative construction energy renovation processes** to face these issues, building in particular on the results of three pilot sites (Paris, San Sebastian and Venice) providing solid elements to evaluate the performance of the BIM4REN innovations.

BIM is too often perceived as a collection of complex tools and work methods that require several weeks of heavy training, often inaccessible to small companies from a financial and practical point of view. The BIM4REN partnership aims to make full use of BIM technology to improve the energy efficiency in situations of refurbishment and renovation of the existing building stock, with a particular attention for construction micro, small and medium-sized enterprises. Top-notch RTOs active in the built environment domain ([Nobatek](#), [CSTB](#), [Tecnalia](#), [TNO](#) and [Fraunhofer ISE](#)) will work alongside key industrial actors ([EDF](#), [CMB Carpi](#) and [ATI Project](#)), Universities ([Aachen University](#) and [Vilnius University](#)), R&D firms ([R2M Solution](#), [COMET](#) and [Ekodenge](#)), technology providers ([IES](#), [EnerBIM](#), [WiseBIM](#), [VRM](#) and [AEC3](#)), SME contractors ([Kursaal](#) and [Termoline](#)), a social Housing organisation ([Logirep](#)), the [Green Building Council- Italy](#) and the [European Builders Confederation EBC](#), the European organisation representing micro, small and medium-sized construction companies.

"Our sector is 94.1% of companies with fewer than 10 employees and 99.4% of less than 49 employees; however, while the digital transformation of the construction sector cannot be done without SMEs, these companies do not have access to it or do not use it", says Eugenio Quintieri, EBC Secretary General, who adds: ***"Digital tools and methods make it possible to alleviate heavy tasks and avoid doubling actions, to improve the image of our professions, to go towards more efficiency, more energy saving and better communication within the value chain, as long as they are financially and technically accessible for SMEs and constitute a real added value!"***

Responsible of 40% of final energy consumption in the EU, the construction industry must contribute to the decarbonisation of the European economy by 2050, in order to reach EU targets of reducing its CO² emissions by at least 80% and its energy consumption by as much as 50%. "***The digital transformation brings results in terms of productivity and energy consumption, especially by bringing the real consumption of the building closer to the expected consumption***", adds Thomas Messervey, CEO of R2M Solutions; who warns that within 5 or 10 years, the transformation lead by digital technology will be even more radical: "***In addition to collaborative platforms and digital models, we will have to learn to work with artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, stand-alone bulldozers, digital twins, cloud and edge computing, and many more digital and intelligent tools.***"

BIM should not only be regarded as a tool for creating and managing high quality construction projects in a faster and cheaper way, but also as a significant opportunity that could reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gases emissions, and as the ultimate trigger for a better collaboration along the whole construction value chain. "***Given the gap between how the use of BIM is designed and the reality of its use by micro, small and medium-sized companies, we must develop powerful tools to attract and involve construction professionals in the deployment of BIM***", concludes Antoine Dugué, the coordinator of BIM4REN.

Indeed, BIM4REN aims at developing a collaborative service platform that engages all stakeholders across the value chain in order to steer digital-driven workflows. In this sense, the BIM4REN consortium will reunite a broad construction stakeholders community, for liaison activities with construction-related entities that might be interested in the results and findings of the BIM4REN project. Feel free to manifest your interest in joining the **BIM4REN stakeholders community!**

For more information on the BIM4REN project, please contact Antoine Dugué, NOBATEK/INEF4 R&D Responsible and BIM4REN Project Coordinator: +33 5 56 84 63 70; adugue@nobatek.inef4.com

For more information on the BIM4REN Stakeholders community, please contact Eugenio Quintieri, EBC Secretary General: +32 2 514 23 23; eugenio.quintieri@ebc-construction.eu

(Pictures) The BIM4REN kick-off meeting took place on 24-25 October in Bordeaux, France.

Note from the editor:

Building Information Modelling (BIM) combines working methods and a 3D parametric numerical model. It matches intelligent and structured data allowing the sharing of reliable information throughout the life of a building or infrastructure, from their design until their demolition. These processes help define and track who does what, how and when across the construction value chain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 820773

3. Social media presence

BIM4REN will endeavour to communicate via two (2) main social media platforms: Twitter and LinkedIn with the objective of promoting the project, disseminating its progress and generating a progressively growing network of members and followers. In both social media we are sharing news, updates, events in which we participate, and other contents of interest.

The activity carried out via social networks is being monitored to ensure that it follows the progress established in the KPIs that will be defined in the Communication strategy (D9.3). The expected goal by projects-end established in the proposal is of 300 group members per social media platform and 10,000,000 impressions / views across all partner feeds.

3.1. Twitter

The Twitter account was published on October 2018 and as of November 29th has 9 Tweets and 40 followers. (Figure 1). Despite the short time, we have had a good reception and we aim to continue gaining support of many multipliers to reach the M12 goal of 70 followers. We have also put in place the hashtag #BIM4REN, currently in use.

We are linked, among other users, to the European Commission and its different agencies and organizations, to the H2020 sister projects, as well as numerous stakeholders, public authorities, investors and potential users.

<https://twitter.com/bim4ren>

3.2. LinkedIn

The LinkedIn page is targeted to professionals, stakeholders, potential users, public authorities and investors (Figure 2). More recently created (at the end of October 2018), as of November 29th it has 30 members which has put us very quickly at almost half of our goal for M12 (70 members).

BIM4REN is currently member of related H2020 featured groups and is already showing good and constant growth: through its publications it has generated 17 likes, 70 clicks and 432 organic impressions.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/geofit-project/>

BIM4Ren
Tweets 7 | Following 48 | Followers 39 | Likes 18 | Lists 0 | Moments 0

BIM4Ren Project
@bim4ren
#H2020 project boosting the #renovation rate in EU through a set of easy-to-use #BIM tools dedicated to collaborative construction energy renovation works.
Europe
Joined October 2018

Tweets | Tweets & replies | Media

BIM4REN Project @bim4ren · Oct 31
Hi people! The @EU_H2020 #BIM4ren project is already launched and underway! We are developing #BIM based tools and technologies for fast and efficient #renovation of residential buildings. Follow us to stay up to date!

Data Management

NOBATEK/INF4 EBC, Tecnalia and 7 others
13 | 18

GBC Italia @GBCItalia · Nov 7
Il futuro della progettazione sostenibile? Il #BIM Strumento efficace, ma ancora poco diffuso per ridurre il #ConsumoEnergia e le #Emissioni #GASemita
Scopri il corso di formazione: bitalia.org/corso-greenbim
Scopri il nuovo progetto europeo #BIM4REN bit.ly/2ZayudM
Translate Tweet

Eugenio Quintieri @eugenioin_bim · Oct 25
For the next 4 years, @EBC_SMEs will work with top experts in the @EU_H2020 @bim4ren project to help SMEs like @kursaaigreen to use #bim in renovation works and test digital tools in pilot buildings. What an emotional kick-off meeting in #Bonn! thanks @Nilsoswinnel!

EBC @EBC_SMEs · Oct 25
Great start in #Bonn! for a very exciting project: so looking forward to work with all @bim4ren partners! #BIM4Ren
Easy #BIM tools for collaborative #energy #renovation processes!
Coup de ♥ for the #construction #SME @kursaaigreen
#H2020 #DigitalConstruction

Who to follow
Tim Krögel @TimKroegel
HITZGAP @HITZGAP

Trends for you
Cristina Cifuentes
Parliament
#CapellaVuelvoACasa
#28Nov
#Bim4renAudencia28N
Xi Jinping
#CarmenaSubeEBI
Javier Fernández
#YoNoGastaria
#NoMeVoyAMarte

Figure 3. BIM4REN Twitter account

Figure 4. BIM4REN LinkedIn Page

4. News about BIM4REN

4.1. Press articles

Below a list of project mentions to date:

BIM4REN project: easy-to-use BIM tools for collaborative construction energy renovation works

http://www.buildup.eu/en/news/bim4ren-project-easy-use-bim-tools-collaborative-construction-energy-renovation-works?utm_source=dlvr.it&utm_medium=twitter

Herramientas BIM fáciles de usar para la construcción colaborativa en obras de rehabilitación energética: Nuevo Proyecto Horizonte 2020 BIM4REN

<https://mejoresedificios.com/herramientas-bim-faciles-de-usar-para-la-construccion-colaborativa-en-obras-de-rehabilitacion-energetica-nuevo-proyecto-horizonte-2020-bim4ren/>

Métiers du bâtiment : numériser ou mourir ?

<https://objectifaquitaine.latribune.fr/business/2018-10-23/metiers-du-batiment-numeriser-ou-mourir-794967.html>

The project is mentioned in a press article about the sister project BIMSPEED

<https://www.pbctoday.co.uk/news/bim-news/energy-efficiency-bim-speed/49544/>

4.2. News

Below is a list of some news that can be seen on some companies' websites:

Article on European Federation for Living Association (Early Adopters)

<https://www.ef-l.eu/our-projects/bim4ren/>

News on R2M (partner of the project) website

<https://www.r2msolution.com/2018/10/30/easy-to-use-bim-tools-for-collaborative-construction-energy-renovation-works-new-horizon-2020-project-bim4ren/>

Kursaal Rehabilitaciones (R2M is a partner of the project)

<https://www.prkursaal.com/es/noticias/2018/10/23/difusin-asesoramiento-y-ferias/kursaal-rehabilitaciones-en-un-nuevo-proyecto-i-d-para-la-implantacin-bim-en-los-procesos-de-rehabilitacin-energtica-de-edificios/1/297>

5. Conclusions

The communication efforts described in this document show that within two (2) months, we managed to start BIM4REN's communication activities through a successful press release and targeted social media presence.

They are the first in a series of actions that will quickly build-up over the next 6 months, mainly the Communication Strategy (D9.3), the project visual identity, the public website (D9.1) at the end of the year, the public dissemination materials (D9.4) and clustering activities (D9.8).

These next steps will allow us to establish a more complex approach and more elaborated contents that will help us expand the understanding of the project and its progress with the objective of allowing us to encourage further engagement and active involvement with stakeholders, multipliers, the general public and end-users for the duration of the project.

6. References

- European Commission (2014, November 17). H2020 Program. Guidance: Communicating Horizon 2020 projects.
<https://ec.europa.eu/easme/sites/easme-site/files/documents/6.Communication-AlexandraRuete.pdf>
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http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf
- European IPR Helpdesk (2018, March). Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation.
<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>
- European IPR Helpdesk (2015). Factsheet: The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020.
https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/FS-Plan-for-the-exploitation-and-dissemination-of-results_1.pdf